

Angel or Devil? – The role of scents in interaction and emotion design

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to discuss the role of scents in interaction design. Scent-output is not an innovative idea in the digital world. From Sensorama (Heilig 1962) to iSmells (DigiScents 2000), people attempt to provide olfactory sensation to enhance user emotional experiences. However, most of them only caught the attention from the media at the beginning, but hardly lasted long in their era. Is it a dream or a gimmick? Do people enjoy having smells with computers? To what extent and in which context can computer-controlled scent output be designed properly? Problems arising from the nature of odour, olfactory technology, and context usages are discussed. Gameplay is used as the template to analysis the challenges and feasibility of using scents to elicit emotions in interactive media. This paper suggests that the problems above could be turned into the features of gameplay. An olfactory game is presented to illustrate the idea.

Conference theme: Usages and Interaction

Keywords: olfactory, interaction, gameplay

Background

In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to design for emotion. More and more researchers and designers show interested in seeking different models and solutions to evoke users' emotions and desires. The release of Norman's book, "*Emotional Design*" (Norman, 2005), is a case in point. Today, design is not only about the product appearances, aesthetes, and usability, but also how users feel about the products. Hana (2007) proposed that the field of design should be sense-driven, rather than technology-driven. Sensory design is one of the approaches to trigger user's emotions. Visual, audio and haptic technologies offer users multi-sensory experiences and promote engagements in interaction design. IMAX cinema, iPhone, wii controller, multi-touch screen are some of the examples. However, there is one sense which is highly related to emotion, has not been widely used yet. It is olfaction.

The role of smell in daily life

The sense of smell is powerful to us in daily life, though unconsciously. We smell with every breath we take. It alerts us the danger of fire and the spoilage food. Infants recognize their mothers by body odours (MacFarlane, 1975). It plays a significant role in retrieving memory. A well-known example comes from Proute's book "Remembrance of Things Past". He recalled his pleasure moments in childhood from the scent of a piece of pastry dipped in tea (Proust, 1955). Over the years, many studies have shown that odour affects people on emotion, perception, behaviour, and decision making on the subliminal level. However, to what extent does it affect people' emotions? Does it affect in a positive or negative way? All of the answers are always disputed (Laing et al, 1991).

On the one hand, some studies show that odours have positive effects on improving mood (Warrem and Warrenburg, 1993), perceiving service with better quality (Michon, 2004), reducing anxiety (Lehrner, 2005), and enhancing learning process (Morgan, 1996). However, on the other hand, some studies indicate that odours bring negative effects in certain circumstances. Children experienced a frustration mood in the presence of unfamiliar odour (Epple and Herz, 1999) Unpleasant odours, like rotting yeast, triggers negative emotion on verbal working memory (Habel, 2007). It is suggested that odours would bring pleasant mood to the users especially those related to the memory of happy experiences, and vice versa (Engen, 1991). Despite different experiences among individuals, the smell of hospital and gasoline, for example, are generally treated as unpleasant odours. However, it is interesting that commercial fragrances are labeled as some people favorite odours while others dislike them as the fragrances make

them headache and sneeze (Classen et al., 1994). This points out that a similar situation would happen in the digital world.

The role of smell in commercial world

Perfume and cosmetic companies, not surprisingly, know how to take the potential of fragrances to elicit people's emotions (Jellinek, 1997). According to Euromonitor International's research, the global fragrance market reached US\$30.5 billion in sales in 2006 (Dodson, 2008). Though some critiqued that branding fails to develop evocative and memorable experiences using the sense of smell (HAQUE, 2004), branding companies keep seeking the best way of using ambient scents. They believe that it not only affects the decision making at the moment of purchase, but also triggers customers' memories and emotional connections to the brand in a subtle way. ScentAir, an olfactory marketing company, helped Sony develop a signature fragrance which is claimed to be appeal to female customers for electronic items (ScentAir, 2007). Though companies, like Sony and Westin Hotels & Resorts, admit that it is difficult to prove that the scents directly give an increase in sales, they cannot deny that the scents do provide more possibilities to create an enjoyable environment to customers. It stimulates an increase in shopping time, number of items purchased, and amount spent (Palmer 2007). Ambient odours have also been used in other areas to elicit people's emotions, such as museums (Aggleton, 1999), casinos (Smith, 2002), fashion (Tillotson, 2003), and live performances (Hill, 2003).

Marketing companies seem to taste the advantage of scents. However, such is not the case while scents are introduced to the digital world. From Sensorama (Heilig, 1962) to iSmells (DigiScents, 2000), many attempts have been made to provide olfactory sensation to enhance user experiences. But, most of them only caught the attention from the media when they were released. They hardly gained accepted among the general public. What are the reasons behind this? Is it the fundamental problem with the nature of odour? Is it the problem arising from olfactory technology? Do users enjoy having smell from computers? To what extend can computer-controlled scent output be used in interaction design, and in which context? What are the challenges remained for interactive designers in this uncharted area? Gameplay provides an environment which involves many issues of interactivity and user satisfaction. Games affect player's emotions, for example, pleasure, exciting, frustration, etc. This paper uses gameplay as the template to discuss the challenges and feasibility of using smell to elicit emotions in interactive media.

Human olfactory system

User plays a crucial role in interaction design. Thus, it is important to know how people smell and how people perceive smell in nature. Comparing with other senses, such as sight and hearing, we know little about the sense of smell. The studies of olfactory are always full of discovery and debate. Human olfactory system is close to the limbic system which involved in emotions and memory. In 1991, Buck and Axel discovered that there is a large gene family, comprised of 1000 different genes for olfactory receptors. This discovery, approved by Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine 2004, explains why human can discriminate 10,000 different odours (Nobelprize, 2004). Lancet et. al. (2003) indicated that at least 50 genes are inactive in some people and active in the others. They suggested that this makes the sense of smell different among individuals. It leads to a situation that some users may distinguish some scents while the others cannot in olfactory design. It is similar to the situation arising from colour blindness in visual design.

Odour discrimination and identification

A person may distinguish between odours, but not able to name what it is. It is involved in two dimensions of olfactory perception. Discrimination is the ability of knowing the difference among various odours, in terms of quality or intensity. Identification is the ability of recognising one odour and being able to tell the name of it. Specialists and enthusiasts may discriminate and identify various kinds of aromas, such as perfume, wine and tobacco. In France, the school “School of Noses” trains the students how to smell (Ahern, 2005). However, in general, people may not have as good sense of smell as the experts. This brings up the difficulties to use smell as informative usage in interaction design. Instead, it could be used for affective usage which is discussed later in this paper.

Odour terminology and classification

The sense of smell is described as “*the mute sense, the one without words.*” (Ackerman, 1996) Until now, there is no standard terminology and classification for odours. Specialists, like perfumers and wine testers, have their own terminology to describe aromas. But, it is not widely used among the general public. In addition, the verbal expressions of smells are very limited. People often borrow terms from other sensory system, like taste, touch, hear and sight (Table 1). They also describe smell related to an object or an environment, such as roses, curry, hospitals, girlfriend’s perfume, etc. It is difficult to describe how something smells to a person who has not smelled it (Ackerman, 1996).

SENSES	EXAMPLES
Taste	Sour, sweet, rancid, bitter, strong
Touch	Hot, cold, heavy, fresh
Hearing	Harmonious, melodious
Sight	Clear, vague, dark

Table 1: Terminology from other senses (Barbara and Perliss, 2006)

The odour classification remains disputed over the years. Amoore (1970) attempted to define seven primary odours, which are ethereal (pears), camphoraceous (camphor), musky (musk), floral (roses), minty (peppermint), pungent (vinegar) and putrid (rotten eggs), as the primary molecular basis of odour. But it is not generally approved even though he added more odours to the classification system in 1982.

Due to the development of fragrance technology, fragrance classification has been modified during the time. In 1983, Edwards introduced the fragrance wheel (Figure 1) which includes four main fragrance families (floral, oriental, woody and fresh.) with three related subgroups (Osborne, 2001).

Figure 1: Fragrance wheel (Edwards, 1983)

Odour Perception

Human olfactory perception can be affected by colours, shapes and words. When the same odour is presented in different colour bottles, the proper matching colour odour has higher intensity and pleasantness ratings than the improper one. For example, the scent of strawberry with colour red bottle has higher ratings than the one with colour green bottle (Zellner et. al., 1991). If the same perfume is put in different coloured and shaped bottles, people would think they are different perfumes (BBC News, 2005). De Araujo et. al. (2005) found that people would perceive the odour is more pleasant if they were told it is cheddar cheese rather than body odour, although they were given the same cheddar odour.

Issues with olfactory interaction design

Due to the nature of odour, there are many challenges with using computer-controlled scent output in the digital world. Five issues are discussed: how (release system control), when (duration control), where (spatial control), what (scents selection) and who (users' feedbacks).

How (release system control)

As mentioned above, the classification and the definition of primary odours are full of controversy. Moreover, odour is fundamentally not additive element, like colour. If odour A combines with odour B, their combination may not smell like either of them. This brings difficulties in defining an agreeable standard of odour model in computers, such as RGB colour model in digital media and HTML in webpage. Though a researcher from Huelva University proposed XML smell language, this initial concept has not been proved yet (The Inquirer, 2005). There are several methods to release scents from computer-controlled scent outputs. For instance, spray, heating, scratch-and-sniff, and air-cannon. In interaction design, the odour needs to be released in a short time. Hence, aerosol spray bottles are proposed in this project.

When (duration control)

In theory, computers can control when to start and stop one odour emitting in the release system. With a good ventilation system, it may help to clear the scent-air in a short time. However, due to the nature of odours, it is almost impossible to “stop” and “delete”, more less “pause” and “undo”. From this point of view, the system (and therefore the user) has less control on olfactory output than the other sensory outputs, like speaker and monitor. Once the odour is emitted, user is passive to accept the outcome. This may explain why the setting of scents output

is always default and unchangeable in most of the existing olfactory display projects. The so-called interaction is only allowed the user decide when to active the olfactory event, like clicking a button to sniff. It may affect user's emotions in interaction. It takes certain duration to spread and disappear in the air. It is like fade-in and fade-out in sounds, from silence to be heard, and vice versa, but with less control. And, it is difficult to have pure environment for a particular scent after several sprays. The space might be filled with all the scented-air. Therefore, different sequence of scent emission may mix up all together at the end. As a result, the only thing the user may do is to physically run away from the game or emotionally reject to play again.

Where (spatial control)

Once the odour is emitted into the air, it easily spreads in the space. Although some olfactory display projects are designed to provide an individual experience, they inevitably affect (or even annoy) the others nearby. Hence, there is a need to have a better spatial control of olfactory output. Yanagida et. al. (2004) attempted to use air-cannon to have a better control of the localised scent for the target user with the aid of nose tracking. However, its accuracy needs to be further proved. AromaJet (2000) proposed that the player may have a wearable scent output, which is put on the player's shoulder. The project, "Fragra" (Mochizuki et. al., 2004) used head mounted display (HMD) with the wired olfactory display. However, these wearable devices may let the player feel uncomfortable during gameplay. If it is too close, the user would inhale directly and sniff. If it is too far, the user may not smell it on time. These settings may make the user feel annoying.

What (scents selection)

In the commercial market, most of the available scents are limited to floral and fruity aromas. Although essential oil and perfume industries could provide thousands of various odour mixtures, it is mainly limited to the pleasant odours. But for games, it may need a wide range of scents to incorporate with associated narrative. For instance, the odour of smoke represents a fire happening in a computer game while the odour of sweat refers to the smelly avatar.

Who (users' feedbacks)

Users can decide if a product is successful or not. Therefore, it is worth to have a look on how people think of using smell with different medium. It may reveal the reasons why Sensorama and iSmell not able to last long in their eras. In 1960, a review published in the New York Times showed how people think about the concept of smell-o-vision. *"Scent of Mystery, though beautifully photographed, was perhaps the only genuine stinker ever produced by the motion*

picture industry.” said Hal Erickson. In 2001, Wired magazine chose iSmell as one of the “Empty Promises” in that year. In 2004, Barry Fox criticised the disadvantages of using smell in computers while Scent Mail was first introduced. *“If my computer started attacking me with smells, I’d be really annoyed. I worry about viruses.”* (BBC World, 2004)

Project

Project Background

In recent years, more and more human-computer interaction (HCI) researchers have noticed the potentials of olfactory display. Barfield and Danas (1996) define olfactory display as “a collection of hardware, software, and chemicals that can be used to present olfactory information to the virtual environment participant”. From this definition, it is implied that most of the HCI studies concern how to use scents to convey information, like notification systems, instead of using scents as ambient odour to affect users emotionally. For instance, Kaye (2001) used two scents, mint and lemon to represent the stock market going up or down in the project “Dollars & Scents”. Nevertheless, Bodnar et. al. (2004) pointed out that olfactory notification is less effective in delivering information than the visual and auditory modalities. Moreover, most of the projects used scent as supplements for other sensory channel, rather than substantive, like the project “Fragra”. Washburn et. al. (2004) also criticised whether olfactory output can improve data visualization or not.

Project Design

Gameplay is an interactive environment which involves many aspects of user interactions and emotions, like usability and the flow of game. In this project, gameplay is used as the preliminary way to explore the possibilities of using olfactory output in interactive media. It is not only concerned how technology can be done, but more about how users react and feel about it. In this case, smell is used as substantive element rather than a supplement for other sensory channel. As mentioned above, people have difficulties in identifying smell. And individuals have different abilities of their sense of smell. However, these issues could be designed as the challenges and the features in gameplay. In this project, the player is required to discriminate, identify and recall the smell in order to accomplish the tasks in the gameplay.

Scent Source

The aerosol air fresher with battery operated is used for the scent source in this project, since it can provide a better tempo control of the release action. It is connected to the 8-channels relay.

Once the computer-control relay is switched on, the relevant aerosol is pressed down. It is easier to control the emission of smell during gameplay. Three types of scents (citrus, lavender and jasmine) are used in this project. It is run by Director MX 2004 with SerialXtra to connect the relay.

Game context design

This project includes two sections. The game scenario is setup with two avatars, a husband and a wife, in a playful landscape with virtual fruits and flowers. In the first stage (Figure 2), player is required to discriminate and identify the scents. Each scent is emitted randomly as the virtual fruits dropping from the tree. In the second stage (Figure 3), the player, represented the husband avatar, needs to identify his wife among six masked women by correctly recalling her scent. The player needs to recall a certain odour which his/she smell earlier.

Figure 2: First stage of the game (discriminate and identify the scents)

Figure 3: Second stage of the game (recall the scents)

Users' feedbacks

There are some observations and findings summarized as below:

Some people found it is interesting to play computer game with smell, since the concept of using olfactory output has not been widely used. However, it also reveals the fact that people in

general are not familiar with the process of using olfactory output in games. It shows that an appropriate instruction for olfactory game is needed. For example, the player can first smell the samples of all the scents at the beginning of the game. It may solve of the problem of different odour perception among individuals.

In the first section, many players can discriminate the difference between the floral scent and the fruity one. But they hardly identify which is which, especially two floral scents (lavender and jasmine). Compared to the second section, players found it is easier to accomplish the first section. However, the second one gets the higher ratings in preference among the players when they were asked to rate their favourite section. By observation (Figure 4), many players laughed as they were required to find out their virtual wife in the game scenario. It seems that the game context is an importance issue in interactive olfactory design. In the second section, computer-controlled scent is associated to the scent of woman in the game scenario. It is represented the abstract meaning, rather than informative meaning as the scent of lavender, for example.

Figure 4: Facial expressions on the users

Discussion on Advantages and disadvantages

Indeed, olfactory output has its own advantages and disadvantages. Some of the disadvantages in informative usage could become as the advantages in affective usage in gameplay. In this paper, they could be summarized as below (Table 2):

FEATURES	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES
Diffusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Attract passers-by's attention ◆ Encourage social interactions between users in gameplay ◆ i.e., kiosk, installations and arcade game in public space 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Limited Spatial Precision ◆ Spread Beyond The Individual ◆ Annoy The People Nearby ◆ i.e., desktop application for single user, alert system in an office
Slow speed of awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Reduce the awareness of delay which happened on real time video playing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Inefficient To Present Information ◆ i.e., hard to synthesize with sounds and the hotspots onscreen
Affective response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Offer the players pleasant experiences with pleasant odours ◆ Let the users engage in the environment emotionally ◆ i.e., let the user have a better impression on the game 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Over-attention ◆ Annoyance ◆ i.e., distract the user, lead the user reject to play
cumulative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Combine different odours in different moments. ◆ i.e., good for representing the abstract history of different odour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Hard to present one pure odour at one moment ◆ i.e., not good for using smell to represent an object
odour identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Provide the challenges for gameplay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Difficult to recall the name of scent name

Table 2: Advantages and disadvantages of using smell in gameplay

Conclusion

From the project shown above, people appear to leave positive feedbacks on the concept of using smell in games. Some players even look forward to its further development. Compared to Sensorama and iSmells, the technology today may do much better than the past. However, the

history of olfactory output development also shows that there are many difficulties in implementing olfactory output in interaction design. It can be simply divided into two types: (A) the fundamental problems in the nature world: lack of odour code models, the difference of olfactory perception among individuals (B) The technical problem in the digital world: limited spatial and temporal control of scents, the leaking and delivery problem of scent releasing systems.

Moreover, the technology and the usage of computer-controlled scent output are still under developed. Therefore, there is no golden rule of interactive olfactory design. It is the process of trial-and-error, especially for game design. Indeed, much more studies need to be done in order to establish a better way of using smell in games. However, meanwhile it makes the design process much more challenging and interesting. Game designers have to find out their own optimal solutions for different games. From olfactory output systems to scenario design, there are so many possibilities and combinations of it. As in the natural world, the role of olfactory output may be subliminal, but yet powerful in the virtual world. In the future, the interactive olfactory design should be further developed and gains more attentions as it does now. It is an unexplored territory to elicit users' emotions in interactive media, especially for games.

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References

- Ackerman, D. (1996). "A Natural History of the Senses," Vintage.
- Aggleton, J.P., and Waskett, L. (1999), "The ability of odours to serve as state dependent cues for real-world memories: Can Viking smells aid the recall of Viking experiences?" *British Journal of Psychology*, 90, 1-7.
- Ahern, T. (2005). "A School for Noses." http://aherncomm.com/about_us/writer/food/206_wine.htm (accessed 28 May 2008)
- Amoore, J.E. (1970). "Molecular Basis of Odor." Charles C. Thomas, Springfield IL.
- Amoore, J.E. (1982). "Odour Theory and Odor Classification." *Fragrance Chemistry* (E.T.Theimer ed.), 27-76.
- AromaJet (2000). <http://www.aromajet.com/> (accessed 28 May 2008)
- Barbara, A. and Perliss, A. (2006). "Invisible Architecture: Experiencing Places Through the Sense of Smell." *Skira*, 115.

Barfield, W. and Danas, E. (1996). "Comments on the use of olfactory displays for virtual environments" *Presence*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 109–121.

BBC News (2005). 'Words can change what we smell', <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/health/4558075.stm> (accessed 28 May 2008)

BBC World (2004). "Click N Sniff." http://bbcworld.com/content/clickonline_archive_23_2004.asp?pageid=666&co_pageid=3 (accessed 28 May 2008)

Bodnar, A., Corbett R. and Nekrasovski, D. (2004). "AROMA: Ambient awareness through Olfaction in a Messaging Application." *ICMI 2004*, ACM.

Classen, C., Howes, D. and Synnott, A. (1994), "Aroma: The Cultural History of Smell." Routledge, UK/ USA/ Canada

De Araujo, I.E., Rolls, E.T., Velazco, M.I., Margot, C. and Cayeux, I. (2005). "Cognitive modulation of olfactory processing." *Neuron*, Vol. 46, 671-679.

Dodson, D. (2008). "Growth upturn in the global fragrances market." *Euromonitor International*, 5 Feb 2008, http://www.euromonitor.com/Growth_upturn_in_the_global_fragrances_market (accessed 28 May 2008)

Edwards M., (1983). "Fragrance wheel." <http://www.find-help.us/fragrance-wheel-article.html> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Engen, T. (1991). "Odour Sensation and Memory." Praeger, New York.

Epple, G. and Herz, R.S. (1999). "Ambient odours associated to failure influence cognitive performance in children. *Dev Psychobiol*, 35, 103–107.

Habel, U., Koch, K., Pauly, K., Kellermann, T., Reske, M., Backes, V., Seiferth, N.Y., Stöcker, T., Amunts, K., Shah, N.J., Kircher, T. and Schneider, F. (2007). "The influence of olfactory induced negative emotion on verbal working memory: individual differences in neurobehavioral findings." *Brain Res* 2007, 1152, 158-170.

HAQUE (2004) "The choreography of sensations: Three case studies of responsive environment interfaces." *VSM 2004 Conference Proceedings*.

Hara, K. (2007). "Designing Design." Lars Müller Publishers, 144 .

Hill, L. and Paris, H. (2003). "On the Scent." *Performance Research*, Cambridge, Routledge.

Jellinek, P. (1997). "The psychological Basis of Perfumery." Edited and translated by Jellinek, J.S., London : Blackie Academic & Professional, 234.

Kaye, J. (2004), "Making Scents: aromatic output for HCI." *Interactions*, 11(1), 48-61.

Laing, D., Doty, R. and Breipohl, W. (1991). "The Human Sense of Smell." Springer, Berlin.

Lancet, D., Menashe, I., Man, O. and Gilad, Y. (2003). "Different noses for different people." *Nature Genetics*, Vol. 34, 143 – 144.

Lehrner, J., Marwinski, G., Lehr, S., Jöhren, P. and Deecke, L. (2005). "Ambient odours of orange and lavender reduce anxiety and improve mood in a dental office." *Physiology & Behavior*, 86(1-2), 92-95.

Macfarlane, A. (1975). "Olfaction in the development of social preferences in the human neonate." *Ciba Found Symp*, 33, 103-117.

Michon, R. and Chebat, J.C. (2004). "Service with a Citric Note: The Interaction Effect of Background Music and Ambient Scent on the Perception of Service Quality." 8th International Research Seminar in Service Management, La Londe-les-Maures, France.

Mochizuki, A., Amada, T., Sawa, S., Takeda, T., Motoyashiki, S., Kohyama, K., Imura, M. and Chihara, K. (2004). "Fragra: A Visual-Olfactory VR Game." SIGGRAPH 2004 Sketches, Los Angeles, CA. <http://www.siggraph.org/s2004/>

Morgan, C.L. (1996). "Odours as cues for the recall of words unrelated to odour." *Percept Mot Skills*, 83(3)(2),1227–1234.

New York Times. "Scent of Mystery (1960)". Reviewed by Crowther, B., http://movies2.nytimes.com/gst/movies/movie.html?v_id=109069 (accessed 28 May 2008)

Nobelprize (2004). "Press release: The 2004 Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine", 4 October 2004, <http://nobelprize.org/medicine/laureates/2004/press.html> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Norman, D.A. (2005). "Emotional Design: Why We Love (or Hate) Everyday Things." Basic Books, 101.

Osborne, G. (2001). "Interview with Michael Edwards." <http://www.basenotes.net/interviews/int-medwards.html> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Palmer, K. (2007). "The Games Companies Play", *US News*, 1 August 2007, <http://www.usnews.com/usnews/biztech/articles/070801/01companygames.htm> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Proust, M. (1955). "Remembrance of Things Past." Translated by C. K. Scott Moncrieff, Terence Kilmartin, and Andreas Mayor (Vol. 7). New York: Random House, 1981 (3 vols).

ScentAir (2007). "Scent Study: Sony Style." <http://www.scentair.com/scentstudies/index.php?subSectionID=0&ssID=3> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Smith, J. (2002). "Sweet Smell of Excess." *Ecologist Online*, http://www.theecologist.org/archive_detail.asp?content_id=392 (accessed 28 May 2008)

The Inquirer (2005). "XML Smell language developed by university." (online article by 23 January 2005) <http://www.theinquirer.net/en/inquirer/news/2005/01/23/xml-smell-language-developed-by-university> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Tillotson, J. (2003). "Smart Second Skin dress." <http://www.smartsecondskin.com/main/description.htm> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Warren, C. and Warrenburg, S. (1993). "Effects of Smell on Emotions." *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 113 (4), 394-409.

Washburn, D. A. and Jones, L.M. (2004) "Could Olfactory Displays Improve Data Visualization." *Computing In Science & Engineering*, Nov/Dec 2004, 80-83.

Weird Magazine (2001). 'Vaporware 2001: Empty Promises', (online article by Farhad, M.)
<http://www.wired.com/news/technology/0,1282,49326,00.html> (accessed 28 May 2008)

Yanagida, Y., Kawato, S., Noma, H., Tomono, A. and Tetsutani, N. (2004). "Projection-Based Olfactory Display with Nose Tracking." IEEE Virtual Reality 2004, March 27-31, Chicago, IL USA, 43-50

Zellner, D.A., Bartoli, A.M. and Eckard R. (1991). 'Influence of color on odor identification and liking ratings.' American Journal of Psychology, Vol.104, 547-561.